

Introducing Test Data Validation for Computer Vision

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Abstract

There is an important role for test data in computer vision. Which situations should be covered by the test data. Is the conclusion. A new solution is proposed in the paper. A standard procedure is devised by the safety community. The analysis of hazard and operability is called Hazard and Operability Analysis. It is designed to search in a systematic way. There are difficult, performance-decreasing situations. A generic CV is introduced. For the first time, apply an extensive model that creates the basis for hazard analysis. Hazop to the CV domain. There is a publicly available list of more than 900. Individual dangers have been identified. It is possible to use this checklist to evaluate existing test datasets. The amount of covered hazard is quantified. We first analyze our approach. The stereo vision test datasets are called Middlebury and KITTI. Second, we are. Six popular stereo matching algorithms are compared against each other. They had an average performance and show that was a clear negative. The influence of the risks. The presented approach is used to evaluate and improve. It is possible to create a common basis for future dataset designs.

1. Introduction

Classes for CV algorithms is not straightforward and requires a deep understanding of the problem domain.

In many critical systems, Computer Vision (CV) technologies play a crucial role in navigation and environmental manipulation. Due to the potential risk to human lives, these systems necessitate a robust safety assessment. However, it is often observed that algorithms with high public benchmark scores perform poorly in real-world scenarios. This discrepancy arises because limited benchmarks are applied to open-world problems. While new proposed algorithms are evaluated based on these benchmark datasets, the datasets themselves rarely undergo independent evaluation.

This work introduces a novel approach to facilitate the safety assessment process, extending beyond the basic scope of benchmarking. For the first time, a proven method used by the safety community is applied to the CV domain. It provides an independent measure that quantifies the challenges in a dataset that test the robustness of CV algorithms.

The typical software quality assurance process involves two steps to provide objective evidence that a system meets its requirements: verification and validation. Verification ensures that the specification was implemented correctly (e.g., no bugs). Validation addresses whether the algorithm meets the original requirements, such as being robust under challenging conditions. Validation is

performed using test datasets as inputs and comparing the algorithm's output against the expected results (ground truth, GT).

While general methods for verification can be applied to CV algorithms, the validation part is more specific. A significant challenge when validating CV algorithms is the vast number of possible input datasets, such as test images (e.g., for 640x480 8-bit image inputs, there are approximately 107,398,112 different test images). An effective way to overcome this issue is to find equivalence classes and test the system with a representative from each class. However, defining equivalence classes for CV algorithms is not straightforward and requires a deep understanding of the problem domain.

2. Related Work

1. Bowyer et al. [6] investigate the challenges associated with validating computer vision (CV) systems and suggest that the application of advanced mathematics is closely tied to specific assumptions. If these assumptions are incorrect, the actual results in real-world scenarios will deviate from the anticipated outcomes.

2. A widely-used platform for evaluating computer vision systems, particularly in stereo matching, is the Middlebury stereo database. Scharstein et al. [32] developed an online evaluation platform that provides stereo datasets consisting of image pairs and corresponding ground truth (GT) data. These datasets depict indoor scenes and are created using a structured light approach [33]. Recently, an updated and improved version was introduced, which includes more challenging datasets and a new evaluation method [31].

3. To provide a similar evaluation platform for road scenes, the KITTI database was introduced by Geiger et al. [10].

4. A comprehensive overview of computer vision performance evaluation can be found in Thacker et al. [39]. They summarize and categorize the currently employed techniques for validating the performance of algorithms in various subfields of computer vision.

5. Some examples of these techniques include: Bowyer et al. [5], who present a work on edge detection evaluation based on Receiver Operator Characteristics (ROC) curves for 11 different edge detectors. Min et al. [26] describe an automatic evaluation framework for range image segmentation, which can be generalized to the broader field of region segmentation algorithms. Strecha et al. [37] present a multi-view stereo evaluation dataset that allows for the evaluation of pose estimation and multi-view stereo with and without camera calibration. They also incorporate GT (LIDAR-based) quality in their method to enable fair comparisons between benchmark results. Kondermann et al. [20] discuss the impact of GT quality on evaluation and propose a method to add error bars to disparity GT. Ponce et al. [29] analyze existing image classification test datasets and report on their findings.

2.1. Robustness

In the safety context, robustness is about the safe handling of abnormal situations or input data in general. In CV robustness is mostly considered to refer to a statistic definition. Popular methods like RANSAC (Random Sample Consensus) [9], M-Estimators [14] in general, or specific noise modeling techniques arose of the need to use systems in “real world applications”. However, these methods are not necessarily tackling the problem of robustness by the safety definition. They do not assess the system’s response to highly unexpected data. In the safety context, the analysis of the vulnerabilities with respect to robustness are based on so-called Fault Injection Methods [12] (e.g. Fuzztesting [38]).

2.2. Risk Analysis

Risk-oriented analysis methods are a subset of validation and verification methods. Basically, all technical risk analysis methods have the goal to assess one or several risk related quality attributes (e.g. safety or reliability) of systems, components or even processes with respect to causes and consequences. In addition, they try to identify existing risk reduction measures and to propose additional ones if necessary. Since the topic of risk identification became relevant, first in chemical industries around 1980, it was also applied to software (see Fenelon et al. [8] and Goseva.

3. CV-HAZOP

The identification and collection of CV hazards should follow a systematic manner and the results should be applicable to many CV solutions. To create an accepted tool for the validation of CV systems, the process has to be in line with well-established practices from the risk and safety assessment community. The most generic method HAZOP [19] is chosen over FME(C)A and FTA because it is feasible for systems for which little initial knowledge is available. In addition, the concept of guide words adds a strong source of inspiration that all other concepts are missing.

The following Sections address the main steps of a HAZOP:

1. Model the system.
2. Partition the model into subcomponents, called locations.
3. Find appropriate parameters for each location which describe its configuration.
4. Define useful guide words.
5. Assign meanings for each guide word / parameter combination and derive consequences as well as hazards from each meaning.

3.1. Parameters

Each location is characterized by parameters. They refer to physical and operational aspects that describe the configuration of the subcomponent. The set of parameters chosen for a single location during the HAZOP should be adequate for its characterization. Table 2 shows the parameters chosen for the location “Medium” as an example1 . 3.4. Guide Words

A guide word is a short expression that shall help to trigger the imagination of a deviation from the design / process intent. Number and extent of guide words must be selected to ensure a broad view on the topic. Nevertheless, their number is proportional to the time needed for performing the HAZOP, so avoiding redundant guide words is essential. ¹See supplemental material for all parameters 2069 The used guide words and their interpretation in the context of CV are listed in Table 1. The first seven “basic” guide words are standard guide words used in every HAZOP and the remainder are adaptations and additions.

3.2. Execution

The actual execution of the HAZOP is the systematic investigation of each combination of guide words and parameters at every location in the system. It is performed redundantly by multiple contributors. Afterwards, the results are compared and discussed to increase quality and completeness. Each HAZOP contributor assigns at least one meaning per combination. In addition, for each meaning found the contributors investigate the direct consequences of this deviation on the system and subsequently into which hazards this can be translated. One meaning can result in multiple consequences at different levels and they are per se not considered harmful or helpful. The hazards, on the other hand, amount to actual decreases in the total system’s performance or quality. Combinations that result in meaningful interpretations by any contributor are considered to be “meaningful” entries while combinations without a single interpretation are considered to be “meaningless”. The execution of the CV-HAZOP, including various meetings and discussions by the contributors (with expertise in testing, analysis, and CV), took one year. Each location is covered by at least three of the authors. The additional experts are mentioned in the acknowledgments. The 52 parameters from all seven locations, combined with the 17 guide words, result in 884 combinations. Each combination can have multiple meanings assigned to it. Finally, 947 unique and meaningful entries have been produced. Table 3 shows an excerpt of entries from the final HAZOP2 . The entries in the list can include multiple meanings for each parameter as well as multiple consequences and hazards per meaning. The whole resulting dataset of the CV-HAZOP is publicly available at www.vitro-testing.com.

3.3. Resulting List

In total, 947 entries are considered meaningful by the experts. A detailed analysis of the resulting amount of meaningful entries achieved for each guide word / parameter combination is shown in Fig. 3. One goal is to maximize the meaningful entries - and the graphic shows reasonably high entries for most of the basic guide words (see Tab. 1). Lower valued entries in the matrix can be explained as well: The concepts of the spatial aspects “Close” and “Remote” are simply not applicable to the properties of the electronic part of the observer (Obs. Electronics) and the concept of space in general is not applicable to a number of parameters at various locations. This also counts for the temporal guide words which are not fitting very well to the Optomechanical ²See supplemental material for more entries and Medium locations. Nevertheless, even here the usage of guide word / parameter combinations inspire the analysts to find interpretations which would have been hard to find otherwise.

4. Application

This paper emphasizes the checklist's application as an evaluation tool for existing datasets.

Creating new test datasets is the next logical step to optimize completeness regarding robustness, but this falls outside the scope of the paper.

Evaluators must first establish the purpose and context of the task.

This specification defines the boundaries for filtering hazards.

The purpose involves defining goals, while the context specifies the conditions and environment where the algorithm should operate effectively.

With purpose and context established, evaluators assess each item in the CV-HAZOP list for relevance to the task.

It can be beneficial to adapt the general hazard entry for readability specific to the algorithm.

Process Outline:

1. Verify if the preconditions in the Meaning and Consequences columns apply.
2. Determine if the Hazard applies to the specific task.
3. If the Hazard entry is too generic, specify it for the specific task.

Other Points:

Previous evaluations for similar tasks can expedite the process and reduce effort compared to reviewing the entire generic list.

Specialized hazards can be added to the checklist for future evaluations.

Evaluators can use the reduced hazard list to examine test datasets and identify their occurrence.

Pixel-based annotations can indicate specific hazard locations in test images (see Sec. 5).

This process reveals missing hazards, which can then be quantified (e.g., 70% of relevant hazards are covered by the test dataset).

This serves as a measure of completeness.

5. Interpretation

The effect of applying the masks based on the identified hazards can be clearly seen. Table 5 summarizes the ratios between the error values of shape and all. The correctly masked areas (shape) have higher error ratios than the mean for the full image (all). The results for KITTI are much more erratic than the rest. The large amount of missing GT data in this dataset reduced its value for this evaluation drastically. The majority of shape mask areas have higher error ratios than the same-sized box mask areas. Newer and more complex algorithms generally score lower errors and have lower absolute differences between shape and all errors. There are two distinct groupings: rand masks have comparable results as all masks while box is comparable to shape 3. This allows for the following conclusions based on the different maskings: algorithms have higher error rates at annotated areas and score even higher error rates if the annotation's shape is preserved (shape vs. box). The effect of sampling patches of different sizes in each image is not prevalent (rand vs. box) and can be neglected. The evaluation paints a clear picture: Areas identified by the CV experts as containing a visual hazard guided by the CV-HAZOP checklist are especially challenging to the CV algorithms. Thus, these challenging areas need to be focused on for robustness evaluations.

6. Conclusion

The development of a comprehensive checklist encompassing critical scenarios and relationships that could potentially compromise the quality and functionality of CV systems is a vital element in the pursuit of systematic validation of CV algorithms. This paper outlines the collaborative efforts of experts from the fields of computer vision and risk and safety assessment to systematically create such a list. To the authors' knowledge, this marks the first time the risk analysis method HAZOP has been extensively applied to the domain of computer vision.

The CV-HAZOP process begins with the establishment of a generic CV model, based on information flow and transformation. This model divides the system into multiple subsystems, referred to as locations. A set of parameters for each location is defined, characterizing the location's individual impact on information. Additionally, special CV-relevant 'guide words' are introduced, representing deviations of parameters that could lead to hazards. The HAZOP execution involves multiple authors working in parallel, assigning meanings to each combination of guide words and parameters to identify hazards. The individual findings are then discussed and consolidated into a single resulting CV-HAZOP list. A guideline for utilizing the hazard list as a tool for evaluating and enhancing the quality and comprehensiveness of test datasets is provided.

The CV-HAZOP has generated a comprehensive hazard checklist for the generic CV algorithm, featuring over 900 unique entries. It supports structured analysis of existing datasets and calculation of their hazard coverage in relation to the checklist. We present an example by applying the proposed guidelines to popular stereo vision datasets and subsequently evaluate the impact of identified hazards on stereo vision performance. The results demonstrate a clear correlation: identified hazards negatively affect output quality.

Our HAZOP checklist is not considered definitive. It will be updated to incorporate new scenarios and relationships as they emerge, ensuring its continued relevance and effectiveness in the field of computer vision.

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